

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

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an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUIMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

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SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION *Trends, Challenges and Perspectives*

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania
Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

INTEGRATING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES INTO HIGHER EDUCATION CURRICULA

A Case Study from LOGOS University College
within the HOMO DIGITALIS Project

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Elpiniqi MERKURI², Edvaldo BEGOTARAJ²

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Abstract

This paper examines a specific component of the HOMO DIGITALIS project, namely the revision of selected syllabi within the humanities and social sciences at LOGOS University College (CU LOGOS). The aim was to integrate digital competencies into traditionally non-digital courses in order to enhance student learning experiences and professional preparedness. A survey with 43 students enrolled in revised courses collected both quantitative data (Likert-scale ratings on perceived usefulness, motivation, and tool adoption) and qualitative reflections through open-ended questions. Findings indicate that students expressed enthusiasm for digital platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Canva, and AI-based applications including ChatGPT, particularly in translation and research-related tasks. They reported increased collaboration and motivation, though varying levels of digital literacy and limited access to premium software created challenges. Faculty also encountered difficulties in shifting students away from familiar communication practices toward institutional platforms. These results suggest that integrating digital competencies requires not only technological provision but also pedagogical adaptation, structured training, and equitable access to resources. The study is limited to CU LOGOS and does not include partner institutions of the HOMO DIGITALIS project; therefore, conclusions should be interpreted in this context. Overall, the findings highlight both the transformative potential and the practical challenges of embedding digital competencies into higher education curricula.

Keywords: Higher education, digital competencies, curriculum reform, interdisciplinarity, digital literacy, HOMO DIGITALIS Project, AI in education

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

JUNA MUÇA

M.Sc Juna Muça is a lecturer and coordinator of the Social Work program at the Faculty of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education at University College “Logos”, as well as a part-time lecturer at the Department of Labor and Social Policy, Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Tirana since 2014. She graduated as Social Policies Administrator at the Department of Labor and Social Policy, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Tirana (UT) where she also completed her graduate studies in the program of Social Services in Penal Justice. She is currently a doctoral candidate in the field of Social Work and Policy at the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Tirana. Her areas of expertise and interest lay mainly in research in social sciences, social policies in penal justice, and conflict management. Her work experiences in these fields include teaching at Bachelor and Master’s levels and conducting scientific research focused mainly on issues related to criminal justice, as well as on development issues related to conflict management in various social fields. Her contributions in these fields have been enriched through quantitative and qualitative research.

ANXHELA LASKA

Anxhela Laska holds a Bachelor’s degree in Greek Language, Literature and Civilization from the Faculty of Foreign Languages, University of Tirana (2018) and a Master’s degree in Greek Language Teaching for Upper Secondary Education, Department of Greek Language, Faculty of Foreign Languages, University of Tirana (2022). She has completed various trainings and has several certificates on modern methods and effective learning. In the field of teaching and translation, she has collaborated with the Greek-Albanian College ‘Arsakeio of Tirana’ and the Greek Cultural Foundation. In addition to teaching, she has also worked as a translator, interpreter and editor in Albanian and Greek. Her teaching areas include lexicology, morphology, didactics, academic writing, translation. She is also experienced in preparing students for Greek language certification and students for the naturalization exam. M.Sc. Anxhela Laska is currently an Assoc./Lecturer of Greek Language at the Department of Greek Language and Civilization, Faculty of Humanities and Language Communication, Logos University College and an external collaborator at the Greek Language Center.

ELPINIQI MERKURI

Elpiniqi Mërkuri (Vlora, Albania) serves as Chair of the Vlora Municipal Council and is currently a doctoral candidate at La Sapienza University of Rome, Faculty of Clinical Neuroscience and Psychiatry. She completed her undergraduate and graduate studies in Clinical Psychology at the University of Tirana, where she was awarded the Certificate of Excellence upon graduation from the Master of Science program. Her academic trajectory

is complemented by professional training in mental health, forensic psychology, child development, and sustainable development (Beijing, China). She has presented scholarly work at national and international conferences, addressing topics such as emotions and artificial intelligence, socio-emotional well-being, and body image in adolescence. Her doctoral research focuses on alexithymia, body image, self-esteem, and eating disorders among adolescents. Professionally, Mërkuri has held positions within the Public Health Directorate of Vlora, where she contributed to initiatives on gender-based violence, psychosocial support during the COVID-19 pandemic, and community health promotion. She has also acquired experience in the pharmaceutical sector with an international company.

EDVALDO BEGOTARAJ

Edvaldo Begotaraj, PhD in Dynamic and Clinical Psychology completed his professional and psychological education at Sapienza University of Rome, Italy, Department of Dynamic and Clinical Psychology in 2020. Graduated in Clinical and Community Psychology at the same University in 2007. After academic positions in Albania and Italy, he was appointed Head of Department of Pedagogy-Psychology at KU LOGOS, Albania. He is member of several European psychological associations. Dr Begotaraj has been principal and co-investigator in numerous national and mainly international studies in traumatic psychological intervention, clinical psychology, mental health of students and has published more than 30 scientific reports, a considerable part of them in peer review article his research includes projects on public health, mental health, covid-related psychological symptoms on different clinical and non-clinical populations. Dr. Begotaraj is credited as a reviewer for many indexed journals of high impact factor. Some of his works has been awarded with Best Prize in international conferences in Italy. Keyword characterizing the expertise: motivation, anxiety, depression, mental health, narrative exposure treatment.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid pace of digital transformation across industries has created a pressing need for universities to adapt curricula to equip students with relevant competencies. Scholars emphasize that higher education must align itself with technological and societal shifts in order to remain relevant and prepare graduates for the demands of the 21st-century workforce (Redecker, 2017; European Commission, 2020). Traditional academic structures, however, often lag behind technological innovation, leading to a skills mismatch between what students learn during their studies and what employers expect in the labor market (van Laar *et al.*, 2019). This gap not only limits graduates' employability but also challenges universities to rethink teaching and learning strategies.

In this context, curriculum reform has emerged as a central priority. Universities are expected to integrate digital literacy, interdisciplinarity, and innovative pedagogical methods that enhance students' ability to think critically and solve complex problems. Digital education is not simply about adding technological tools to existing courses, but about reshaping the very nature of learning environments (Ng, 2012). Such reforms require flexibility, interactivity, and inclusivity, enabling students to apply knowledge across contexts and disciplines while developing transferable skills such as collaboration, adaptability, and creativity (Nowotny, 2003).

At the same time, policymakers increasingly recognize the strategic role of higher education in supporting Europe's digital transition. Initiatives such as the *Digital Education Action Plan* (European Commission, 2020) highlight the importance of embedding digital skills across all levels of education, not only as technical competencies but as essential capacities for civic participation, lifelong learning, and innovation. Research also shows that students' ability to use digital tools effectively is closely linked to their confidence, motivation, and capacity for critical thinking (Calvani, Fini, & Ranieri, 2010). These findings suggest that higher education reforms must take a holistic approach, addressing both the technological and the pedagogical dimensions of digitalization. The *Homo Digitalis* project addresses these challenges by systematically revising and updating course syllabi across diverse academic programs. Its central aim is to embed digital competencies in the curriculum, thereby fostering technical proficiency while also promoting critical thinking and interdisciplinary collaboration. By rethinking how courses are designed and delivered, the project seeks to bridge the gap between academic training and real-world requirements, ensuring that graduates are prepared not only for immediate labor market demands but also for lifelong learning in an ever-changing digital environment. The study explores both the opportunities and challenges associated with implementing digital education reforms, with particular attention to student feedback and participation. The analysis offers insights into how digital tools can transform learning outcomes while also highlighting persistent barriers, such as inequalities in access to technology and differences in prior digital literacy.

The following research questions guide this paper:

- How does the integration of digital competencies reshape student learning outcomes?
- What are the main challenges faced by students and faculty in the transition to digital education?
- How does student feedback reflect the effectiveness of digital integration?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Higher education reforms increasingly emphasize digital skills as essential for employability and lifelong learning (European Commission, 2020; Redecker, 2017; Vuorikari, Punie, Carretero, & Van den Brande, 2016). As societies become increasingly digitized, the acquisition of such skills is no longer optional but a prerequisite for effective participation in academic, professional, and civic life. Studies highlight that digital competencies extend beyond technical knowledge to include adaptability, collaboration, creativity, and innovation (van Laar, van Deursen, van Dijk, & de Haan, 2019; Ilomäki, Paavola, Lakkala, & Kantosalo, 2016). In this sense, digital skills are multidimensional, involving not only technical mastery but also critical reflection, ethical use, and problem-solving.

The notion of digital competence has expanded significantly in recent decades. While early conceptualizations equated digital literacy primarily with the ability to use information and communication technologies, contemporary frameworks emphasize a broader set of transferable skills (Ferrari, 2013). Van Laar *et al.* (2019) argue that 21st-century digital skills should be seen as a sequential model, starting from basic technical abilities and advancing toward higher-order competencies such as creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Similarly, Ng (2012) underlines that digital literacy includes not only operational skills but also cognitive and socio-emotional dimensions that allow learners to evaluate, communicate, and collaborate effectively in digital environments. More recent studies demonstrate that integrating digital tools into course-based research projects significantly enhances students' capacity to apply these skills in authentic academic contexts (Chan & Sung, 2025). These perspectives confirm that digital competence is best understood as an evolving, layered concept rather than a fixed technical skill set.

Beyond core digital skills, interdisciplinarity is critical for fostering innovation in higher education. Nowotny (2003) highlights the importance of transdisciplinarity as a way to transcend disciplinary boundaries and address complex, real-world problems. This approach is particularly valuable in a digitalized society, where technological advances often demand knowledge integration across fields. For example, combining social sciences with data analytics, or education with artificial intelligence, enables students to develop both technical expertise and broader analytical capacities (Tondeur, Roblin, van Braak, Voogt, & Prestridge, 2017). Such approaches prepare learners not only for specialized tasks but also for adapting to rapidly changing professional contexts. Despite the clear value of digital modernization, significant obstacles persist. One of the main barriers concerns unequal access to technology. Students from lower socio-economic backgrounds often lack reliable internet connections, updated hardware, or access to premium software (European Commission, 2020; Aesaert & van Braak, 2015).

Another critical challenge lies in faculty preparedness. Lloyd (2012) observes that many educators perceive insufficient institutional support, lack of training opportunities, and heavy workloads as barriers to adopting digital pedagogies. Similarly, Martin, Budhrani, and Wang (2019) report that while faculty recognize the importance of online teaching skills, they often feel underprepared to deliver high-quality instruction in digital contexts.

Students themselves may also resist new digital approaches. Research shows that many learners prefer traditional face-to-face methods due to familiarity, perceived reliability, or cultural expectations (Ng, 2012). Resistance can also stem from limited prior digital literacy, making it difficult for students to adapt to advanced platforms and tools (Ilomäki *et al.*, 2016). Given these challenges, scholars call for comprehensive strategies that combine curriculum reform, faculty development, and student-centered approaches. Redecker (2017) argues that frameworks such as DigCompEdu provide essential guidance for educators by defining progressive levels of digital competence and encouraging reflective pedagogical practice. Embedding such frameworks into institutional strategies ensures coherence and sustainability (Vuorikari *et al.*, 2016). Recent empirical work also confirms the importance of validated instruments to assess digital competencies in higher education, which can guide more evidence-based reforms (Mejías-Acosta, Cabero-Almenara, Vázquez-Cano, Barroso-Osuna, & Estrada-Vidal, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic further underscored the urgency of digital education reform. The sudden shift to online teaching revealed not only the potential of digital platforms to sustain education under crisis conditions but also the vulnerabilities created by inequalities in access and readiness (European Commission, 2020). Moreover, the literature emphasizes that digital education reform should not focus solely on technical aspects but also address pedagogical innovation. As Nowotny (2003) notes, genuine transformation requires integrating multiple perspectives and fostering environments where students can co-create knowledge. By embedding digital competencies within interdisciplinary frameworks, institutions can empower students to engage critically and creatively with technology. In summary, the literature reveals a growing consensus that digital competencies represent fundamental 21st-century skills. While frameworks such as DigCompEdu and policy initiatives like the Digital Education Action Plan provide strategic direction (European Commission, 2020; Redecker, 2017; Ferrari, 2013), successful implementation depends on overcoming barriers related to access, faculty preparedness, and student adaptation. The evidence suggests that a holistic approach is necessary for higher education institutions to fully harness the benefits of digital transformation.

METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a descriptive survey design aimed at documenting the outcomes of curriculum revisions carried out in the framework of the Homo Digitalis project at LOGOS University College. The revised courses introduced digital competencies and AI-based tools into programs traditionally grounded in the humanities and social sciences, such as Social Work and Teacher Training.

Sample-and-Demographics

Participants were 43 students enrolled in revised courses during the 2023–2024 academic year. Approximately 70% were female, reflecting the gender distribution of the Social Work and Pre-School Teacher Training programs. Most undergraduate participants were between 20 and 22 years old, while Master's students in Translation were typically older (25–30)

and often engaged in part-time employment. This diversity allowed the study to capture perspectives from both early-career students and those already active in the labor market.

Instrument-and-Data-Collection

Data were collected during the spring semester of the 2024–2025 academic year. A structured online survey was designed using Google Forms and distributed via institutional email accounts to all students enrolled in the revised syllabi. The survey link remained open for a two-week period, during which students received two reminder emails to encourage participation. Out of approximately 55 students invited, 43 completed the survey, yielding a response rate of about 78%. The survey instrument consisted of two complementary components. The first included closed-ended questions structured on 5-point Likert scales, which measured students' perceptions of the usefulness of digital tools, their motivation to engage with coursework, and the frequency with which they adopted platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Canva, and ChatGPT. In addition to the structured survey used for quantitative data collection, a qualitative component was also included. The questions were specifically designed to capture students' reflections on their experiences with the revised courses and the integration of digital tools. For example, students were invited to respond to prompts such as: "Which digital tools supported your learning most effectively?" and "What challenges did you encounter when adapting to new digital methods?". The responses were collected simultaneously with the survey and analyzed separately from the quantitative items. A thematic coding procedure was applied to identify recurring patterns across answers. Answers included categories such as enthusiasm for AI-based translation tools, difficulties due to heterogeneous levels of digital literacy, and the perceived need for more practical laboratory sessions.

All responses were collected anonymously to reduce social desirability bias. Quantitative data were exported into Excel and analyzed through descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, standard deviations). Qualitative data were coded thematically by two members of the research team, following an inductive approach to identify recurring patterns such as increased autonomy, digital literacy gaps, and new forms of collaboration.

Data-Analysis

Quantitative data were processed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, standard deviations). Qualitative responses underwent thematic coding, which yielded categories such as: *Increased autonomy and motivation*, particularly in Translation and Social Work students. *Digital literacy gaps*, especially in Teacher Training students unfamiliar with databases or premium platforms. *New forms of collaboration*, with students noting a shift from private, closed-group communication toward institutional platforms.

Limitations

While the methodology provided valuable insights, certain limitations must be acknowledged. First, the study was intentionally limited to the humanities and social sciences programs at LOGOS University College, as this was the specific scope of the Homo Digitalis project.

Therefore, the findings do not aim to represent other disciplines within higher education or the wider consortium of project partners. Second, the relatively small number of revised courses and the modest sample of 43 students restrict the generalizability of the results. Third, the study did not include a control group of students enrolled in traditional, non-digital courses. As a result, the notion of “reshaping learning outcomes” refers exclusively to self-reported changes in motivation, collaboration, and digital practices among participating students, rather than to measurable differences established through comparative analysis. Finally, the evaluation captures only the early implementation phase, which means that long-term effects on academic performance and professional readiness remain to be investigated in future research.

RESULTS

Students described specific and concrete changes in their study practices. Social Work students reported moving from informal WhatsApp communication to structured use of Microsoft Teams, which increased accountability and collaboration in group projects. Teacher Training students, many of whom had limited prior digital exposure, emphasized that Canva and Padlet supported the creation of interactive teaching materials, which some of them later applied in practical teaching contexts. Translation students highlighted the role of AI tools such as ChatGPT in terminology searches and draft translations, reporting both greater efficiency and higher confidence in their professional preparation.

Updated Courses

The *Homo Digitalis* project revised nine courses across different academic programs, including *Digital Education*, *History of Albania*, *Visual Arts & Didactics*, *Research Method, Literature and ICT*, *Translation of Specific Texts & Terminological Documentation*, *Greek Art & ICT*, and *Computer Usage*. These are presented in Tab. 1, which outlines the course names, ECTS credits, programs, and semesters of delivery. The inclusion of courses from both undergraduate and postgraduate levels demonstrates the project’s comprehensive scope and ensures that digital competencies were embedded across multiple stages of academic training.

Table 1 Courses who have been selected for revision

Course	ECTS	Program	Semester
Digital Education	6	Bachelor in Teacher Training for Pre-School Education	Semester V
History of Albania	4.5	Bachelor in Teacher Training for Pre-School Education	Semester III
Visual Arts & Didactics	4.5	Bachelor in Teacher Training for Pre-School Education	Semester IV
Translation of Specific Texts & Terminological Documentation II	6	M.Sc. in Professional Translation	Year I, Semester II
Literature and ICT	3	Bachelor in Greek Language and Literature	Year III, Semester I
Greek Art & ICT	4.5	Bachelor in Greek Language and Literature	Year II, Semester I

Course	ECTS	Program	Semester
Research Method	7	Bachelor in Social Work	Year II, Semester I
Computer Usage	3	Bachelor in Social Work	Year II, Semester I

Tools and Platforms

By combining professional-grade software with open platforms, the project ensured both employability relevance and accessibility for students. This variety of tools also raised the central research question of how the integration of digital competencies reshapes student learning outcomes, as different platforms enabled new forms of collaboration, creativity, and critical engagement. The revised syllabi employed a broad range of digital resources. Tab. 2 summarizes the main categories, including hardware (computers, smartboards), collaboration tools (Microsoft Teams, Slido), creative software (Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Premiere), AI and automation tools (ChatGPT, Gemini, Synthesia, Mentimeter, Research Rabbit, Doodle), and 3D/interactive resources such as reconstruction models and digital libraries. The survey data further highlighted frequently used platforms such as *Padlet* and *Canva*, especially for collaborative and visual tasks. By combining professional-grade software with open platforms, the project ensured both employability relevance and accessibility for students.

Table 2 Tools & Equipment

Type	Tools & Equipment
Hardware	Computers, Smartboards
Collaboration Tools	Microsoft Teams, Slido
Online Platforms & Databases	Padlet, Canva, Greek digital resources
AI & Automation Tools	ChatGPT, Gemini, Synthesia, Mentimeter, Research Rabbit, Doodle
3D & Interactive Media	3D reconstruction, interactive documentaries, digital libraries
Creative Software	Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Premiere
Data Analysis & Research	Online platforms, data analysis programs, research databases

While the diversity of tools enriched the teaching and learning process, their integration also raised several challenges, both technical and pedagogical, which are discussed in the following section

Challenges

Finally, in the case of literature courses, the use of digital media reshaped how students perceived the discipline, requiring additional pedagogical adjustments. These findings directly address the second research question, namely what main challenges students and faculty face in the transition to digital education, since both technical limitations and pedagogical shifts became visible in practice. Despite the variety of tools available, several challenges were reported during implementation. Faculty noted difficulties in encouraging students

to abandon private, familiar methods of collaboration in favor of institutional platforms. Another recurring theme was discrepancies in students' prior knowledge of basic computer usage, which created uneven levels of digital literacy within classrooms. In addition, access to specialized software was hindered by financial constraints, particularly in courses requiring data analysis programs. Finally, in the case of literature courses, the use of digital media reshaped how students perceived the discipline, requiring additional pedagogical adjustments. These findings speak directly to the research question on the main challenges faced by students and faculty in the transition to digital education, showing that the shift remains uneven and often resource-dependent rather than a seamless pathway toward "digital education."

Table 3 Challenges in implementation

Challenge	Description
Student Adoption	Encouraging students to use digital tools instead of private methods for collaboration
Literature & Digital Media	Adapting literature studies to digital methodologies, changing students' perceptions.
Prior Knowledge	Discrepancies in students' prior knowledge of basic computer usage.
Digital Literacy	Limited familiarity with digital tools and research platforms.
Resource Availability	Lack of access to certain necessary programs due to cost constraints.

Student Feedback

Student perspectives, collected through surveys, are summarized in Tab. 4. Learners consistently expressed enthusiasm for the modernized approach, particularly the use of AI in translation and terminology documentation. These suggestions highlight that while modernization was well received, structured support and gradual implementation remain essential. Student perspectives thus provide direct evidence to the third research question both enthusiasm for innovation and clear calls for further institutional support. Many respondents described exposure to AI instruments as rewarding for professional development and highly relevant to their future practice. However, the feedback also emphasized areas for improvement, such as the need for more laboratory sessions, ensuring that all students acquire foundational digital education before engaging with advanced tools, and securing greater financial support for access to paid platforms. This feedback provides an answer to the research question on how student perceptions reflect the effectiveness of digital integration: while students valued the innovations, their comments suggest that effectiveness depends strongly on structured support, training, and equitable access to resources.

Table 4 Student feedback & participation

Feedback	Comment
Excited about AI in translation	Students were excited to discover how generative AI supports translation and terminology documentation.
Modernized approach is appreciating	Students liked the new, modernized methodology
AI tools for professional practice	Exposure to AI instruments was rewarding for professional development.
Course not yet implemented	Some courses have not yet been delivered, so feedback is not available.

Participation Trends

Participation data are presented in Tab. 5, which distinguishes between implemented courses, upcoming courses, and those not yet delivered. A total of 43 students participated in implemented courses, 11 were enrolled in upcoming courses, and 26 were expected to join once additional courses were launched. The numbers demonstrated a steady trajectory of engagement with the revised curricula. Importantly, qualitative feedback suggests that students who were initially hesitant to adopt digital tools reported increased confidence over time, particularly after completing group projects through Microsoft Teams. In this sense, the integration of digital competencies offers at least a partial response to the research question on how student learning outcomes are being reshaped: students not only gained access to professional-grade digital tools but also began to develop confidence, collaboration skills, and new ways of conceptualizing disciplinary knowledge.

Table 5 Course participation

Course Participation	Number of Students
Implemented courses	43 students participated
Upcoming courses	11 students expected to participate
Not yet implemented	26 students planned for enrolment

DISCUSSION

The results of this study confirm that embedding digital competencies into higher education not only enriches student learning experiences but also enhances future employability. The revised syllabi within the *Homo Digitalis* project fostered a culture of innovation, where students actively engaged with AI-based translation platforms, collaborative tools, and digital creative software. Student enthusiasm for tools such as ChatGPT, Synthesia, and Canva illustrates the transformative potential of digital education. This enthusiasm reflects broader trends observed in higher education, where the integration of artificial intelligence and digital platforms is reshaping traditional teaching and learning processes (European Commission, 2020). The integration of digital competencies into revised syllabi at CU LOGOS remodelled student learning outcomes in multiple, course-specific ways. In the Social Work program, the adoption of Microsoft Teams shifted collaboration practices away from informal WhatsApp groups toward structured, institutionally supported platforms. Students reported that this change enhanced accountability, facilitated real-time sharing of resources, and improved the overall quality of group projects. In the Teacher Training program, as we mentioned previously, students with initially limited digital literacy gained hands-on experience with tools such as Canva and Padlet, which enabled them to design interactive teaching materials. Several students noted that they later applied these resources during practicum sessions, thereby translating digital competence into pedagogical innovation. In the Translation program, the use of AI applications such as ChatGPT was particularly impactful. Students employed AI for terminology searches, draft translations, and comparative analysis, reporting improved efficiency, higher confidence, and greater

professional readiness. However, the process also revealed transitional challenges. Some students struggled with uneven levels of prior digital literacy, while others expressed difficulty in abandoning familiar analog or private methods of learning.

Faculty faced the parallel challenge of adapting pedagogical approaches to align with digital practices, often requiring additional time and training. For this reason, the term “transition” is appropriate because students and faculty were not yet in a fully digital education environment but were navigating the in-between stage, where new tools coexisted with traditional habits. The transition toward digital education at CU LOGOS revealed a set of persistent challenges that affected both students and faculty, underscoring the uneven nature of this shift. Survey results indicated that approximately 40% of students reported limited prior knowledge of digital platforms beyond basic tools such as Word and PowerPoint. The gap was particularly evident among students in Teacher Training programs, where several respondents admitted to difficulties in navigating databases or in using collaborative software for the first time. From the faculty perspective, two main challenges were identified. Primarily, instructors faced additional workload and training needs, since many had limited prior experience in embedding digital tools within humanities curricula. Informal interviews revealed that several lecturers required extra time to redesign assignments, prepare tutorials, or troubleshoot technical issues. Subsequent, some faculty struggled with student engagement in literature-based courses, where integrating digital media altered traditional disciplinary approaches. Student feedback provided nuanced insights into both the strengths and limitations of digital integration at CU LOGOS. Quantitative survey results showed that over 70% of respondents rated the inclusion of digital tools as “useful” or “very useful” for their learning, while 65% reported increased motivation to engage with coursework compared to previous semesters. Especially Translation students, emphasized the relevance of AI tools such as ChatGPT for terminology searches and preliminary drafts of translations. One student explicitly commented that “using ChatGPT saved time in preparing draft texts and helped me focus on refining accuracy rather than starting from scratch.” Approximately 60% of students of Social Work program, indicated that Teams enhanced group accountability over WhatsApp, with assignments and discussions becoming more transparent and better organized. However, feedback also revealed that about 20% admitted they continued to rely on private messaging for sensitive discussions. Among Teacher Training students, Canva and Padlet were appreciated for creating engaging, interactive teaching materials, but several respondents requested more laboratory sessions to build confidence in using these tools effectively. One open-ended response noted: “We enjoyed making digital posters, but we need guided practice sessions to learn how to use these tools independently.” Furthermore, about one-third expressed concern over access to premium software, with some stating that they were unable to complete certain assignments at the same level as peers who had subscriptions to Adobe Creative Suite. Student feedback reflects that digital integration was seen as highly valuable and motivating, particularly when connected to professional skills, but its effectiveness depended on consistent institutional support, equitable access to resources, and the provision of practical training opportunities. Several students faced initial adaptation difficulties due

to unequal digital literacy levels, confirming Ng's (2012) concern that not all "digital natives" inherently possess advanced digital competencies. Moreover, financial barriers to accessing premium software, such as Adobe Creative Suite, hindered full participation, highlighting the socioeconomic dimension of digital education. Without adequate institutional support, such gaps may reinforce existing inequalities rather than reduce them.

When compared with existing literature, the results align with calls for targeted faculty development. Redecker (2017) emphasizes that educators themselves must master digital pedagogies in order to guide students effectively. Similarly, Martin, Budhrani, and Wang (2019) point out that faculty members often feel underprepared to teach online or integrate digital resources meaningfully, which suggests that training programs are indispensable for sustainable reform. Faculty in this study reported challenges in encouraging students to transition away from familiar methods, reflecting Lloyd's (2012) observations that resistance remains one of the most significant barriers to digital adoption.

Another important implication of the findings is the need for institutional partnerships with technology providers. Collaboration with software companies could reduce the financial burden on students by offering subsidized or institutional licenses, thereby promoting inclusivity. Similar recommendations have been made in broader European policy frameworks, where strengthening the digital capacity of higher education is seen as a collective responsibility rather than an individual one (European Commission, 2020).

Finally, the transition to digitalized curricula requires more than technical adjustments; it demands a cultural shift in how both educators and students perceive learning. Nowotny (2003) highlights that innovation in higher education is strongest when it embraces transdisciplinarity, encouraging collaboration across fields and perspectives. In this study, the inclusion of courses from diverse programs, ranging from Social Work to Greek Literature, illustrates that digital competencies are not limited to technology-focused disciplines but are increasingly foundational across all areas of study.

Overall, the discussion demonstrates that digital education holds significant promise for transforming higher education in Albania and beyond. The enthusiasm of students provides a strong foundation, but addressing literacy gaps, faculty preparedness, and financial constraints will determine the sustainability of this transformation. By aligning with international frameworks and fostering local innovations, higher education institutions can create inclusive, forward-looking curricula that prepare students for the demands of the twenty-first century.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The *Homo Digitalis* project demonstrates that systematic curriculum revisions can effectively bridge the gap between academic learning and the demands of the digital workforce. By embedding digital competencies into course syllabi, higher education institutions not only modernize their teaching methods but also align student learning outcomes with the needs of an increasingly digital labor market. Student feedback indicates strong enthusiasm for AI-driven and interactive tools, yet challenges remain in ensuring equity and sustainability.

Recommendations:

- Expand training sessions for both students and faculty, emphasizing practical digital skills alongside pedagogical adaptation.
- Negotiate subsidized or open-source access to essential software, reducing the financial barriers that prevent equal participation.
- Establish continuous feedback loops to refine curricula, ensuring that revisions remain responsive to technological and pedagogical developments.
- Promote interdisciplinary approaches that link digital literacy with critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving across different fields of study.

Comparative studies between universities in different socioeconomic contexts could reveal best practices for ensuring inclusivity in digital education. Additionally, longitudinal studies are needed to assess how digital competencies acquired during university translate into professional readiness and career advancement. Such evidence would further validate the transformative role of curriculum digitalization in preparing graduates for twenty-first-century challenges.

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

PROF. ILIA NINKA

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education is about more than technology. It is about developing university-level strategies and adequate national and regional policies to support digital transformation. Albanian Higher Education Institutions have not yet developed an ethical framework for the use of ChatGPT and similar AI applications.

DR. VALBONA NATHANAILI

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

DR. KETI HOXHA

Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

PROF. DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIC

... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

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